

Inexpensive X-band ½ Watt PA using 3D LTCC Technology

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Abstract — We report the development of a very low cost (\$5.00), self-packaged, broadband (5-11 GHz), power amplifier (PA) based on 3D LTCC technology. The PA has more than ½ watt output power across the band.

I. INTRODUCTION

The recent boom in wireless communications underscores the need for providing inexpensive microwave circuits and higher levels of on-chip integration. A promising approach is to build three dimensional microwave circuits by laminating multiple microwave circuit layers on top of each other while keeping all active devices on the semiconductor layer.

The 3D approach lowers cost by saving valuable real estate space [1]. This area is receiving increased theoretical attention [2]-[3]. Several multilevel MMIC circuits have been reported [4]-[6].

One of the technologies that facilitates the use of 3D concepts is Low Temperature Cofired Ceramic (LTCC). This is a cost-saving technology that is being implemented to lower the cost of RF components for cellular and GPS applications by lower the component count (resistors and capacitors are embedded in one substrate). However, the LTCC technology also exhibits low loss at C, and X-bands. At these bands, the cost savings are even greater. This is why we chose to demonstrate the use of both the 3D and LTCC technologies to dramatically cut the cost of C- and X-band circuits.

II. CIRCUIT DESIGN

Our goal is to dramatically cut the cost of C, and X-band RF components. One of the most expensive components is the PA. Our goal was to design a broadband PA with at least ½ Watt output power and with 10 dB of gain. A two-stage approach was chosen to ensure gain in excess of 10 dB across the band. The active devices used were AMCOM PHEMTs with gate width of

1.2mm (for driver stage) and 2.4mm (for power stage). For cost savings, a hybrid circuit approach was chosen. The reason is that real estate is more expensive on GaAs substrate than on LTCC substrates. The LTCC substrate shall contain all the RF matching circuitry, most of the low frequency stabilization circuitry, plus the thermal vias for heat removal under the PHEMT devices. The LTCC material selected was DuPont 951 tape with mixed silver and gold conductors. The reason is that this is a widely used, low cost tape, that does not require special processing. Also the via holes were filled with silver (instead of gold) to save on cost. Also the fact that the LTCC substrate acts as a carrier/package by itself, saves the cost of a high priced ceramic package required, otherwise. Hence, this should lower the cost.

The number of layers used is 5 layers with thickness 3.5, 5.1, 5.1, 3.5, and 3.5 mils respectively. Figure 1 shows the layout and layer stack up. The top 3 layers are used for RF lines, and the bottom two layers are used for low frequency bypass capacitors. The first (top) metal level is used for RF lines. The second metal level is used for both bottom capacitor plates, and (in some area) as elevated ground level. The third metal level is not used (has no metal). The reason this layer is there is to add thickness to the substrate, for RF and mechanical rigidity purposes. The fourth metal level is used as RF ground. It also serves as upper ground for low frequency circuitry below. The fifth metal level is used for low frequency bypass capacitors. The sixth (bottom) metal level is the lower ground level for low frequency bypass capacitors. The different grounds (at 2nd, 4th, and 6th levels) are connected with vias. The stacking of low frequency and RF lines helps compact the overall circuit area. The amplifier dimensions is 0.25" x 0.495" (about 1/8 of an inch square).

One of the design issues that has to be overcome is that in that the LTCC medium does not accommodate ground planes with more than 50% area coverage. This means that instead of having a solid ground plane, we have to use a

gridded ground pattern. This has very minor effect on RF performance [7].

The other great advantage of LTCC technology is that it lowers the cost in two ways. First, the LTCC substrate is sturdy enough that alleviates the need for an expensive ceramic package (able to handle the power dissipation and work at high frequency). Second, it allows for using SMT parts directly on the substrate.

From a RF design point of view, the LTCC environment offers a very unique 3D advantage. Specifically, the ability to move the ground level up or down allows for a wide range of transmission line impedances. This give great flexibility to the designer and allows for compact designs. The only thing that has to be observed is that the transition between different ground levels has to be simulated carefully to account for the transition discontinuity. In our case, this was done through full wave analysis of the ground-level transitions.

Fig. 1a: Layer stack up. Top metal is layer 1. Layer 2 is used as RF ground (sometimes), or as bottom plate for capacitors. Layers 4, and 6 are as grounds.

Fig. 1b: Layout of PA. Ground layers (4, and 6) are hidden. A low frequency stabilization capacitor (on fifth layer metal) is shown, "Embedded low Freq Cap." The elevated RF grounds (on second layer metal) is marked "GND 1". Vias connecting various layers together are shown. Many vias connect ground

layers 2 to 4, and 4 to 6. Both types of vias do not intersect the top level metal.

Fig. 1c: 3D view of PA. The darker metal patches are elevated RF grounds on second layer metal.

Fig. 1d: Picture of top (left) and bottom (right) of LTCC substrate. All ground planes had to be gridded to comply with LTCC technology rules.

Fig. 1e: Picture of assembled PA. Four surface mount (SMT) capacitors (used for low frequency stabilization) are visible.

III. MEASURED RESULTS

The parts were fabricated, assembled, and tested. The parts were built at National Semiconductor. The LTCC substrate included embedded printed resistors.

The measured results are shown in Figure 2. The gain goal (> 10 dB) was achieved over the 4.5-11 GHz. The output power achieved was above 27 dBm across the 5-11 GHz band. In fact, over the 5.5-7.5 GHz band, more than 1 Watt was measured.

One can run a quick cost comparison between our approach and the traditional approach of building a MMIC, and packaging it in a high power, high frequency ceramic package. The cost advantages of our approach are far greater than the traditional approach.

fig. 2. Gain, output power, and input and output return loss.

	MMIC	LTCC
Price per chip (4 mm sq)	\$24.00	--
Price for 2 devices (0.5 mm sq)	--	\$3.00
Assembly cost	\$0.25	\$0.50
Package	\$15.00	--
LTCC Matching Circuit	--	\$0.50
Lid	\$0.60	\$0.75
Testing	\$0.25	\$0.25
Total (direct cost)	\$40.10	\$5.00

Fig. 3. Cost comparison between packaged MMIC and our LTCC hybrid approach.

IV. CONCLUSION

We developed a broadband 3D C-Band through X-band PA with 1-Watt output power (5.5- 7.5 GHz) and ½ Watt output power over the full band (5-11 GHz). A low cost readily available approach was used. The material selection was also driven by cost. The overall performance combined with the exceptional low cost combine to make the 3D LTCC approach very attractive. The same approach can be extended to lower the cost of Ku-band circuits.

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